

D9.1: Data Management Plan

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ABSTRACT:	This report provides a first version of the Data Management Plan for the project. It provides an overview of the type of data that will be collected and how FAIR principles will be applied within XR4HUMAN.
Keyword List:	Data, DMP, FAIR

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1 Data Summary

The main goal of the XR4HUMAN project is to conduct research that adds to the existing body of knowledge on the benefits of eXtended Reality (XR) technologies, while simultaneously addressing the novel ethical and safety challenges that come with the proliferation of these technologies. The project intends to foster the adoption and improvement of XR technologies in human-centered applications, while proactively mitigating any potential risks related to privacy, security, safety, and interoperability issues.

The project will collect data through workshops and interactive stakeholder events, generating various types of data, such as text transcripts, sound files, images, and videos. Following the Grant Agreement, as far as possible data generated will be archived in an EU-recognized trusted repository (Figshare) and in file formats that are open and non-proprietary, guaranteeing FAIR data sharing.

This is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the project, which will be updated regularly as part of XR4Human's deliverables. Future updates will include more technical details such as file size and actual formats of the data generated.

2 FAIR Data

Data generated will be archived and published in the University of South-Eastern Norway's Research Data Archive (USN RDA) after going through a data curation process by the Research Data Management group at the University Library (USN UB). USN RDA is the institutional repository of USN and hosted by Figshare. Alternatively, in case of data that holds significance for a particular field of study or due to convenience considerations of relevant XR4Human partner(s), data may be stored in a trusted repository that may be discipline-specific and adheres to international standards for FAIR data sharing. Future DMPs will reflect these updates. Figshare uses DataCite metadata schema and generates machine-actionable metadata that can be indexed by most search engines (including Datacite and Google Dataset Search) and other national data registers. Using this standard, data will be described comprehensively with extensive and rich metadata to ensure FAIRness. Digital items archived in the USN RDA are assigned a DataCite DOI upon publication and accessed by their identifier using a free and standard communication protocol (HTTPS). Data under embargo can also be provided a DOI or a private link for external partners to be given access to it (e.g., journal article reviewers).

Some of the metadata elements that facilitate FAIRness within the USN RDA include the title of the research project, the names of the author and co-authors, a description of the data, an abstract that summarizes the research, funding details (such as grant project name, acronym, and number), publication date, version number, categories that define the research discipline, keywords that describe the data, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), licensing information (Creative Commons), title and link to the related publication, and links to any reference or related content.

By including these metadata elements, the USN RDA helps to ensure that the data is searchable and discoverable, accessible to others who may want to use it, and that the information relating to the reuse is made clear. Should discipline-specific metadata be needed, data curators in the USN UB can include them after consultation with the research project team. Additionally, a human-readable ReadMe file, which comprehensively discusses the digital item being archived, is a mandatory document required in the data curation process. Data generated by the project will be made publicly available following its completion using a CC-BY license, except for conditions stipulated in the Grant Agreement.

The repository is in constant development to adjust to the evolving field of FAIR data sharing and Open Science practices. The institution has Open Science and FAIR Research Data policies that guide how to manage the repository to ensure the reuse of data generated in all USN-affiliated projects.

3 Other Research Outputs

The Grant Agreement governs the research outputs of the project. To promote Open Science, scientific articles will be published in open access journals, and data resulting from the project will be archived in the USN RDA. This ensures that research outputs of the project are easily accessible and reusable by a variety of potential users, including other researchers, educators, policymakers, and members of the general public.

Since the project is in its initial phase, and other research outputs that are of value may be generated as the project progresses, this part will also be updated in the next DMPs.

4 Allocation of Resources

USN provides data storage solutions as part of the institutional infrastructure and research data management support services through the University Library (UB). These services are offered for USN-hosted projects with no added cost. Should the project produce data that requires an added layer of security, this DMP will be updated to reflect these updates.

5 Data Security

For the duration of the project, data will be securely and confidentially stored in a GDPR-compliant storage solution. The coordinating institution offers project data storage in our local network. The project network drive is backed-up on a daily basis and access is restricted to project members. This storage solution is approved for Red (Confidential/Sensitive) data in the Norwegian classification system.

At the end of the project, data will be archived in USN RDA hosted by Figsare. Figsare stores data for up to 10 years but can be extended if needed.

6 Ethics

There is no immediate ethical or legal issue in data-sharing for the project. The project team will also work closely with the Research Data Management group embedded in the USN UB, which includes a data privacy specialist and a research ethicist, to ensure that data storage, processing and sharing is in line with laws and regulations that govern the conduct of research.

The project will generate qualitative data from workshops and interactive stakeholder events. Participants will be fully informed about the planned archiving of anonymized data in USN RDA and will be asked for their informed consent. In certain circumstances, it may be impossible to anonymize data effectively, or future use may need to identify particular informants/respondents. In these rare cases, bespoke informed consent will be sought at the time of data collection to make the non-anonymized data available on request by bona fide researchers. However, since these are hypothetical scenarios, this would have to be discussed by the project members and the data privacy specialist, and any changes that deviates from the initial DMP will be discussed in the updated versions.

7 Other Issues

There are currently no foreseeable issues related to research data management. The project will adhere to the data management procedures in the coordinating institution, which are based on current industry practice in the EU and Nordic region. However, should special needs/issues arise, the project DMP will be updated, including a discussion of the rationale for the changes implemented.